

**Let the
dialogue
begin**

D6.4: USER ENGAGEMENT AND DISSEMINATION SUPPORT TOOL STRATEGY AND SET UP

Project: **Cross-sector dialogue for Wildfire Risk Management**

Acronym: **Firelogue**

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
D	Deliverable
EO	Earth Observation
EC	European Commission
EARSC	European Association of Remote Sensing Companies
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
IA(s)	Innovation Action(s)
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
TechMall	Technology Mall
WFRM	Wildfire risk management
WP	Work package
UCPKN	Union Civil Protection Knowledge Network
DRMKC	Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre
EU	European Union

Executive Summary

This document (D6.4) presents the strategic actions necessary for the effective engagement of the different stakeholder clusters targeted by the Firelogue. Produced as the fourth deliverable of WP6, it is closely linked to and building on the first three deliverables: the Communication Strategy and Action Plan (D6.1), the Dissemination Strategy and Action Plan (D6.2) and the website (D6.3). Also, D6.4 has received input from the Stakeholder Clustering Report (D7.2) that creates a clear and targeted view of the stakeholders related to Firelogue, towards achieving the best possible impact and engagement WFRM community.

The methodology for stakeholder engagement presented herein will be monitored and refined against the progress of the project's activities throughout its lifetime. The document is structured as follows:

- **Section 1** introduces the importance of stakeholder engagement.
- **Section 2** provides an overview of the stakeholder clusters targeted by Firelogue; outlines the stakeholder engagement strategy which is driven by the main objectives of the project and provides an overview of the timing and tools that will be used.
- **Section 3** focuses on the Communication Booster; analyse its context and added value and lists the most important features that have been discussed till today.
- **Section 4** summarises the deliverable and presents the way forward.

1 Introduction

Firelogue, as an EU project, brings together expertise from all around Europe when it comes to Wildfire Risk Management. From researchers to civil society organisations, Firelogue partners have the experience, the knowledge, and a forward-thinking attitude that places them at the front and centre of all WFRM aspects. Firelogue aims to create dialogue and empower the WFRM community to face the current and future wildfire challenges and acts as an exchange enabler of knowledge through the aggregation of experience and best practices of all stakeholders.

To achieve the project's mission, a coherent stakeholder engagement strategy is needed to align with the related IAs ([DRYADS](#), [SILVANUS](#), [FIRE-RES](#)) and the [FirEUrisk](#) project. Working jointly with the IAs and FirEUrisk, Firelogue targets relevant stakeholders and adapts the engagement activities to their needs. Firelogue's mission is to boost communication within the WFRM community and society, as well as retain and share the knowledge and the experiences gathered alongside the showcase of innovative actions, solutions, services and products.

The following sections will outline the ways that stakeholders will be engaged as well as some key tools to:

- Raise awareness and construct a smooth and effective dialogue within the wildfire sector
- Stimulate and provoke the cooperation and synergies of the different actors in the WFRM community
- Empower the WFRM community to face the current and future wildfire challenges
- Provide inputs and learn from each other's best practices and expertise
- Support and inform relevant stakeholders about project activities and main outcomes
- Spread Firelogue's and IAs impact in the WFRM community

Stakeholders' engagement is fundamental for Firelogue and other wildfire-related projects to be successful, as all are cooperative projects having an impact on the communities they represent. Firelogue has set long-term goals for the environment, climate change and the impact of fires on people and societies towards the impact dimensions mentioned in the call.

2 Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

The establishment of an effective, well-coordinated and sustainable relationship with the various stakeholder clusters relies on an appropriately differentiated methodology that is informed by and tailored to the needs and priorities of each cluster. Firelogue has developed several key messages that are critical in attracting the interest of the various stakeholders to the project (D6.1) and setting the stage for the different ways in which these stakeholders can be involved in the project activities. In this document, the main considerations on how to reach out to different stakeholders are embedded within a strategy that follows Firelogue's strategic objectives.

It is essential to engage various stakeholders across the value chain, e.g., the scientific community, policy making bodies, towards the better exploitation of wildfire data and services. In the framework of Firelogue, this is directly linked to enhanced participation in and contribution to the implementation of the IAs and FirEUrisk's results to the Fire Community. So, a synthetic overview of the stakeholder engagement activities is provided below, and

the engagement is explained explicitly. The stakeholders' engagement activities will be considered by all the Firelogue consortium in order to establish what level of engagement is required, the timing and role of the engagement, and ultimately which methods of engagement are to be adopted for each one.

2.1 Stakeholder identification

At the current stage, Firelogue has identified and clustered stakeholders that may be able not only to contribute to the project but also to motivate them to become involved. Deliverable 7.2 proposed a Stakeholder clustering resulting from the analysis of the individual clustering made by the IAs and [FirEUrisk](#). The stakeholders included in this clustering have been grouped into 8 categories, each containing a number of stakeholder profiles involved — either directly or indirectly — in wildfire risk management and risk reduction strategies. These categories are:

- **Emergency management organisations**, e.g., firefighters; civil protection; medical services and police; first responders performing operations in the field; fire analysts.
- **Scientific community**, e.g., research and academic institutions involved in diverse scientific areas related to wildfire management; fire safety engineers.
- **Policy making bodies**, e.g., administrations acting at different territorial levels; EU commissioners; politicians.
- **Land management groups**, e.g., landowner associations; land planners; farmers; foresters, whose activity has direct implications over fuel load management through burning, cutting, grazing and other activities.
- **Environmental associations**, e.g., conservation organisations; environmental consultancies; environmental educators.
- **Media**, e.g., journalists; communicators in the environmental field; social media influencers.
- **Society**, e.g., social groups; volunteer associations; representatives for certain citizen groups; vulnerable groups.
- **Industry, technology, and innovation**, e.g., the industry around sectors of energy, construction, infrastructures, timber, fire prevention and firefighting equipment; Banking, Financial Services, and Insurance industry.

2.2 Stakeholder assessment and analysis

The next stage of an efficient stakeholder engagement process includes the assessment and analysis of stakeholders in relation to the necessity for their engagement. It has been noted that each stakeholder or group of stakeholders does not need to be involved on the same level of engagement, or at the same time of the project, while the same stakeholder may be engaged through different ways at the various stages of the project implementation.

To determine which stakeholders are best to contribute and which will be affected by the project, and therefore critical to involve, it is important to take into account the relevance of stakeholders with Firelogue. It is considered necessary to identify their interests and roles in relation to Firelogue's objectives and to understand them according to their importance to and influence on Firelogue. Table 1 is an indicative list of each stakeholder cluster, possible reasons for them to be involved and their expected benefits through involvement. As "Reason

for inclusion” is our motivation to get them involved (Why we want to get them engaged?), whereas “interests/benefits” refers to what they can get from getting involved in the project (What they can get from it?).

Table 1: Stakeholder clusters, reasons to get involved and their interest in Firelogue

Stakeholder clusters ¹	Reasons to involve	Interests / benefits
Emergency management organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of technical expertise to the project • Testing, evaluation & validation of wildfire related projects' output/results • Implementation & Replication of solutions • Provision of tactical and strategical advice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase citizens' trust • Networking • Raise awareness • Access to innovative tools (e.g. early warning systems) • Exchange of best practices
Scientific community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of access to relevant research results • Foster research • Sharing scientific expertise and provision of advice • Evaluation & approval of project outputs • Expertise/know-how in domains related to fire sector (e.g. earth observation, biodiversity) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publications • New research opportunities / widening expertise • New potential collaborations with industry • Networking • Empowering existing results • Stimulate research talents • Transfer of theory to praxis • Verification of usefulness of research results for operational scopes
Policy making bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation & approval of projects outputs • Foster dissemination of results • Provision of access to assure usefulness & relevance of project outputs • Mainstream adaptation into relevant policies • Promote wider adoption & replication of project outputs • Liaison with other entities & involvement of citizens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enrich a database of experiences and best practices on WFRM issue • The exploitation of results for the improvement of policy-making • Opportunity to develop better policies based upon rigorous scientific knowledge • Funding opportunities for necessary projects • Harmonisation with EU policies • Gain the trust of society in decisions taken

¹ The titles of the stakeholder groups are based on the titles given in D7.2 - Stakeholder Clustering Report

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be part of feasibility studies and pilot projects • Raise awareness among the local population, regional and/or national administrators, EU Commissioners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge expansion in new sectors
Land management groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation & approval of related project outputs • Ensure usefulness & relevance of project outputs • Foster adoption of project results through the implementation of best practices/solutions • Better networking with organizations and linking to individuals (e.g. farmers) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use the new technologies produced by the wildfire-related projects • Adoption of environmentally friendly practices in a cost-effective way • Cross-sector collaboration • Strengthen trust with relevant authorities and with the scientific and technical community who are developers of knowledge and tools they can make use of.
Environmental associations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation & approval of project outputs • Ensure usefulness & relevance of project outputs • Foster dissemination and adoption of project results • Exercising pressure on governments & companies • Better networking with organizations and linking to individuals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use the new data and services produced • Adoption of environmentally friendly practices • Raise awareness inside the value chain for promoting environment • Transfer from theory to practice • Raise public awareness on environmental issues
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wide dissemination of project results • Link to citizens • Influence people's behaviours, beliefs and attitudes about wildfire risk and the resulting WFRM strategies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Material for stories/news • Raise awareness • Communicate the progress of the entire WFRM community • Promote Firelogue and wildfire related projects' results
Society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exercise pressure on governments & companies • Augment engagement of volunteers and citizens • Ensure project outcomes are accepted and adopted • Test wildfire related projects' services and inform the wider public for any topics that may be of their interest 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safer societies, more fire-resilient • Protection from climate change impacts • Economic benefits and reduction of losses to livelihoods, assets • Information about new technologies and response to a wildfire event

Industry, technology and innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diffusion of the project results for incorporating WFRM related issues in their risk plans (e.g., Banks, insurance) • Widen business and knowledge network • New tools to be commercialized • Know-how in sectors related indirectly to the fire sector • Development of operationally-oriented tools based on practitioners' requirements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Minimise the financial risk of non-accounted factors through Firelogue and wildfire related projects' results • Introduced to new technologies • Reduction of building losses • Access to innovative systems (e.g. early warning) • Learning about/adopting on new tools and strategies • Create innovation to make more business for their customers • Strengthen trust with relevant authorities and with end-users of the services, products and tools they will develop
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2.3 Stakeholder engagement

The establishment of an effective, well-coordinated and sustainable relationship with the various stakeholder groups relies on an appropriately differentiated methodology that is informed by and tailored to the needs and priorities of each cluster. After previously identifying (section 2.1) and analysing the various stakeholders (section 2.2), we need to identify their envisioned 'level' of engagement, which ranges from the lowest level ('inform'), through the middle levels ('consult' and 'involve') to the highest level ('collaborate' and 'empower').

The description of the different levels can be found below:

- **Inform** (little interest in or influence over project outcomes): Stakeholders should be adequately updated with information on the Firelogue and IAs scope, problems addressed, objectives and outcomes to assess the available alternatives, recognise opportunities and discover potential solutions. The information must always be tailored to the specific needs of each stakeholder cluster.
- **Consult** (high interest - low influence - may prove particularly useful by forming alliances with other more influential stakeholders): Stakeholders should be informed and consulted on several project's issues (e.g. the methodologies applied for joint impact assessment) as well as provide some feedback. Care will be taken so as to not overwhelm stakeholders with information outside of their area of expertise/interest.
- **Involve** (little interest or low capacity – highly influential): Stakeholders should work directly with Firelogue and IAs throughout the duration of the project to ensure that their concerns and requirements are well understood, taken into consideration and, where appropriate, are satisfied by the projects' actions.
- **Collaborate** (high interest – high influence - impacted by the final project outcomes): Stakeholders should work in partnership with Firelogue and IAs, in relevant aspects of the entire process, e.g., for co-creating and co-designing as well as validating some initial products. This includes any actions necessary for ensuring that these stakeholders remain fully satisfied, such as the identification of

preferred solutions or outcomes.

- **Empower:** Stakeholders should provide Firelogue with information and solutions that they use and already possessed to offer better and more targeted services and thus strengthen the existing ones. Then, they can be benefited by adopting services/solutions/products developed by IAs. Firelogue creates a sense of trust with these stakeholders and exchanges constructive feedback, most probably close to the end of the project or beyond its lifetime.

It is important to obtain a greater understanding of stakeholders' motivations, interests, expertise, and capacity to engage. The following key points are considered during the process of understanding stakeholders are provided:

- Existing relationships between Firelogue and stakeholders
- Existing relationships between IAs and FirEURisk and stakeholders
- Knowledge of what the different stakeholders possess that may be relevant to Firelogue
- Potential positive or negative views of the stakeholders on IAs outcomes.
- Potential for any conflict arising amongst stakeholders or between stakeholders during Working Group discussions
- Appropriate means of communication and need to be adapted to reach certain groups or individuals
- Willingness to engage; if not, reasons and means for overcoming the problems.

2.4 Timing

The expected inputs/outputs of stakeholder engagement are also defined by a temporal component. Firelogue do not intend to overburden the stakeholders and be considerate of their limited time, thus involvement should be as low as possible (and only be increased if explicitly expressed by the different stakeholder). Thus, as different project activities kick-in different dimensions of stakeholder engagement, Table 2 below, categorizes the type of engagement according to the type of stakeholder and timing in the project, early (first 18 Months), middle stage (Month 18-Month 48) and after the lifetime of the project till 2030.

Table 2: Stakeholder Engagement throughout the Project life cycle

Stakeholders ²	Early Stage (M0-M18)	Middle Stage (M18-M48)	Beyond Project's life (till 2030)
Emergency management organisations	<p>Inform</p> <p>Need to inform early with concise formal ways to ensure awareness and willingness to participate.</p>	<p>Inform & Consult</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involve by inviting them into events and keep informed especially about Innovation Actions events, news, and initiatives • Promote demonstration exercises where they can test, validate and provide general feedback on the solutions 	<p>Inform - Collaborate - Empower</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keep them in the loop and invite them in the major events especially if they were involved. • Collaborate with IA activities. • Embody new services and knowledge as new and more effective solutions for wildfires

² The titles of the stakeholder groups are based on the titles given in D7.2 - Stakeholder Clustering Report

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure their involvement with IAs services/ solutions. • Receive feedback related to IAs services targeting them 	
Scientific community	Inform & Consult <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to inform early with concise formal ways to ensure awareness • Vital to establishing high-level communication as early as possible. • Have key contacts to use for collaboration and empowerment later. • Ensure good communication between them and IAs for knowledge exchange 	Inform-Consult-Involve-Collaborate <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintaining an open communication channel at high levels is essential for them to engage in any substantial way. • Create a professional environment for joint publications with the IAs 	Inform & Empower <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keep them in the loop and invite them to major events especially if they were involved or collaborated with any IA activity. • Make sure that they attend as they are sometimes regional key actors. • Boost them towards beyond state-of-the-art research. • Enrich the scientific research on WFRM
Policy bodies	Inform & Consult <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inform early in concise formal ways. • Vital to establishing high level communication to create mutual trust between them and IAs. • Need to consult to show a willingness to listen to them • Have key contacts to use for collaboration and empowerment later. 	Inform & Consult <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain high level communication • Show willingness to listen to their needs. • Essential to have key stakeholders as they are usually the regional key actors • Transparency with regards to results and issues is a must to show reliability. • Establish trust. 	Inform & Empower <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain high level communication. • Adoption of developed innovative tools • Engage at the highest level to ensure attendance and always have one-on-one meetings with National /regional administrations to establish interest and actions using formal channels of communications. • Ensure meetings with high level official key actors
Land management groups	Inform <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informing them early and consulting them will help identify relevant issues faster. Their initial response will identify key 	Inform-Consult- Involve <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keeping them in the loop of potential results and developments is essential to maintain their interest but needs to be concise up to 	Inform & Empower <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Keep them in the loop and invite them in major closing events especially if they were involved in an IA and or have collaborated as part of the project stacks.

	<p>stakeholders that can be used for the end stages of evaluation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Need to showcase benefits upfront. 	<p>the point and to showcase the benefits to them.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consider different methods (more focused) of information for stakeholders or individuals (e.g. farmers) working in the private sector. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Invite all involved departments well in advance to ensure that some will be present.
Environmental associations	<p>Inform</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Informing them early and with clear facts. Need to showcase benefits upfront to ensure interest. 	<p>Inform-Consult- Involve</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keeping them in the loop is essential to maintaining their interest but be concise. Ask for expertise in environmental practices Need to notify them early, and focus on the ones used for the IAs. Involve them to ensure WFRM activities are compatible with nature conservation 	<p>Inform & Empower</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keep them to the loop and invite them to the major closing events especially if they were involved or collaborated with any IA activity. Provide them with operational useful IAs tools/solutions
Media	<p>Inform</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Informing them early and with clear, easy to understand facts. Need to showcase the impact of projects to ensure interest. 	<p>Inform</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Need a constant stream of information preferably with easy-to-understand clear messages and imagery. 	<p>Inform</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clear dissemination of the results of the project along with ways of getting involved.
Society	<p>Inform</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inform them early and with clear and easy to understand facts. Need to showcase benefits upfront to ensure interest. 	<p>Inform & Consult</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Need a constant stream of information preferably with easy-to-understand clear messages and imagery. Receive feedback from citizens' associations and volunteers Include them in the loop for getting feedback of projects processes when needed. Use their feedback to improve. 	<p>Inform</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clear dissemination of the results of the project along with ways of getting involved.
Industry, technology, and innovation	<p>Inform-Consult</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inform them early about projects' missions 	<p>Inform-Consult-Involve- Collaborate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keep them in the loop of potential results and developments is essential to 	<p>Inform & Empower</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keep them in the loop and invite them to the major closing events especially if they were involved in an

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consult them to identify relevant issues faster as they are experts. Their initial response will identify key stakeholders that can be used for the end stages of evaluation. Need to showcase benefits upfront. Be aware about the end-user requirements in WFRM to developed operationally-oriented tools that users can see value on it 	<p>maintaining their interest and their needs to be concise, to the point</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure they are informed about the new technologies and solutions provided Showcase the projects' outputs benefits to them. Consider different methods of information for Industry stakeholders. Need to find alternative ways of engaging. 	<p>Innovation Action and or have collaborated as part of the project's tasks.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensure high level official key actors are informed about operational services.
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This analysis process aims at indicating the varying levels of engagement required throughout the project and will be reviewed periodically throughout the project duration for a number of reasons, including:

- I. stakeholders may wish for less or greater involvement at different stages of the project than those originally identified;
- II. new stakeholder groups may also state their willingness to be involved;
- III. needs may arise for engaging stakeholders over subject matter or issues that were not foreseen at the moment;
- IV. there may be a shift in the direction of the project or its outcomes which should be communicated.

2.5 Respective Tools

Table 3 outlines suggested ways and the respective tools to engage stakeholders in general according to each of the five engagement levels (inform, consult, involve, collaborate, and empower). The table can be used to determine the existing stakeholder engagement situation within the scope of Firelogue, what level of engagement the new process is intended to achieve and how different levels of engagement might be appropriate for different purposes.

Table 3: The Stakeholder Engagement Spectrum and respective Tools

	Inform	Consult	Involve	Collaborate	Empower
Goal	To provide balanced, objective, accurate and consistent information to	To obtain feedback from stakeholders on analysis, alternatives and/ or outcomes	To work directly with stakeholders throughout the process to ensure that their concerns and needs are consistently	To partner with the stakeholder including the development of alternatives, making decisions	To create efficient, safe, and targeted solutions and technologies towards preventing

	assist stakeholders to understand the problem, alternatives, opportunities and/or solutions		understood and considered	and the identification of preferred solutions.	disasters from wildfires
Why	It is used at the start of a process, with the promise of more opportunity to participate later.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To improve an existing service through end-user feedback. • Local community (End users) interests can understand and relate to these options. • Use feedback to choose between or modify options. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tap into stakeholder skills and experience to carry out plans. • Stakeholders that have shown a strong desire to participate • Spread the knowledge to the fire community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders 'own' the development and implementation processes. • The various interests involved all get some extra benefit from acting together. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Achieve the reductions of wildfires' impact to the environment and climate change • Create a more sustainable and safer environment also for the citizens
Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flyers • Website • E-news • Newsletters • Oral communication 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working groups discussions • Survey • Workshops • Hands-on exercises with tools developed by the projects • Participation in demonstration pilots 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops • Working groups discussions • Surveys /questionnaires • Engage in preparation (create realistic scenarios) and participation (undertake appropriate performance of the exercises) of demonstration pilots 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint Events • Working groups discussions • Collaborations with IAs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct dialogue between stakeholders and IAs • Demonstrations • Joint planning of services

All the above-mentioned tools will be used to engage the stakeholders in the best possible way. The key to Firelogue's engagement strategy is the Communication Booster tool, a platform of knowledge and interlinkages as outlined below.

3 Communication Booster

Firelogue, in its effort to connect services and stakeholders, plans to create a platform as an interface that is called also “Communication Booster”. This platform will become an area of information, innovative solutions, and services supplied by the IAs. This allows to provide one face to the European Union and being able to distribute the IAs’ results in a coordinated manner as well as to redirect any WFRM related requests from the fire community to the IAs and additional WFRM stakeholders.

The platform will be created based on the following 5 objectives:

- Promote an integrated and multidisciplinary approach to WFRM, addressing:
 - All phases of the disaster risk management cycle (Prevention and Preparedness; Detection and Response; Restoration and Adaptation)
 - All relevant actors’ needs in the different fields of WFRM
- Have a European, multi-level focus by promoting cooperation and exchange of knowledge and experiences between the different countries and actors at the local, national and EU levels.
- Link top-down and bottom-up approaches to WFRM.
- Built on existing initiatives, formats and knowledge and develop complementary content.

3.1 Goal, Content and Added value

The goal of the Communication Booster is to be used by a broad network of partners, collaborators and stakeholders within different areas of WFRM. It is developed to optimize the IAs’ outcomes by facilitating the exchange of information among the actors, creating critical mass, avoiding duplications, and increasing the visibility and impact of Firelogue and IA outcomes. Hence, it is significantly reducing the risk of developing and replicating similar systems and removes traditional organisational and geographical boundaries. The Communication Booster will aim at fostering and increasing European, and international cooperation, collaboration and communication inside the fire community.

In a wider perspective, the added value of the Communication Booster and its expected impacts can be summarized as follows:

- Increase the scientific and technological excellence
- Facilitate integrating and transfer of knowledge to develop a joint research plan and to carry out joint integrating and multilateral activities between partners, collaborators and stakeholders
- Establish a critical mass via networking of researchers with complementary expertise, capacity building and knowledge transfer
- Make common research efforts between the IAs and FirEUrisk, as well as other related projects, allowing for more significant results
- Facilitate proactive studies, sharing standardized and innovative measures in various WFRM related technologies
- Allowing long-lasting research, tools and methods for capitalizing on the IAs’ results
- Enhance communication and visibility at a European and international level
- Deliver knowledge and provide efficient scientific support for strategic and political decision-making

in the WFRM community.

3.2 Features

Discussions between Firelogue and the IAs' partners are ongoing since the beginning of the project regarding the Communication Booster and the tools that need to be integrated into it. Some of them are the ones described below, although final decisions will be made after analysing the Survey results (T1.1), the Clustering Event discussions (April 2022) and more meetings to be held with all actors to understand community's needs and assess their usefulness as well as in agreement with the relevant contact people from the IAs. In the sub-sections below, we refer briefly to some of these features, which are structures in four basic pillars and Figure 1 shows the basic structure of the platform:

1. Hub of existing platforms: Linking, not integrating existing platforms and initiatives
2. Knowledge Management & Communication: encompassing several subsections as detailed below
3. Networking: Connecting People
4. Other Functionalities

Overall, the proposed platform will contain a complete suite of data and content management with categorization and visualisation features that help organisations present public data in easily understandable formats:

1. User roles and authentication

The proposed application provides a complete graphical user interface for creating and managing user accounts and user roles. Additional roles can be created, and rights can be created. The categories of users include:

- (i) **Administrator:** has all the rights to manage the application and will remain with owners of the platform.
- (ii) **Editor:** Has limited administrator rights and will remain to key Firelogue partners. Has the right to add a user. To change the structure of the website by adding for example menus. Change some elements in groups and datasets. It can view and edit all groups and datasets.
- (iii) **Registered user:** Has no access to the admin menu and can add groups and datasets.

2. Registration

There are three registration methods available to be discussed.

- (i) From the User Registration Menu
- (ii) Via Social Media Icons.
- (iii) The administrator can add a user from the administration menu.

3. Content Updates

The Firelogue Communication Booster will be an environment that is dynamically refreshed and curated so that all external stakeholders can stay up to date with the latest developments, news, events, milestones, etc. A team,

consisting of the communication manager, the dissemination manager, and key members of Firelogue will be responsible for regular content updates, further facilitated by augmented functionalities, as the website becomes a portal.

Figure 1: Communication Booster structure

3.2.1 Hub of existing platforms

3.2.1.1 Platform Hub

One of the biggest challenges we face in developing the platform is that although there is a variety of services that have been created, there is lack of connection and integrated exposure to their wide communication. The Firelogue platform wanting to fill this gap aims to perform as a Platform Hub. The Platform Hub will be a connection of all existing fire-related platforms by linkages with the more important ones, so the interested

stakeholder will be able to find information about the content each platform provides useful contact information and a direct link to the corresponding page. Indicatively, an initial list of sources of interest to be examined includes the platforms below, however, before making any formal linkages, we will need to check the platforms' metadata and whether they rely on open standards:

1. [Lessons on fire](#)
2. [UCPM Knowledge Network Platform](#)
3. [FIRE IN](#)
4. [SAFERS](#)
5. [FIRE LINKS](#)
6. [DRMKC Gaps explorer](#)
7. [OFFIDIA](#)
8. [FIREFRONT](#)
9. [FIRES](#)
10. [EFFIS](#)
11. [WE ADAPT](#)
12. [FIRESAFE EUROPE](#)
13. [FFIS](#)
14. [Fire Hub](#)
15. [NextGEOSS](#)
16. [GeoPortal](#)

Targeted stakeholders: Emergency management organisations; Scientific community; Policy making bodies; Land management groups; Environmental associations; Industry, technology, and innovation; to find condensed information and to navigate more targeted through the different platforms.

3.2.1.2 Library

The aim of the library is to link to other well-known open platforms in order to include:

- 1) information on relevant past and ongoing Research and Innovation projects from local to global level, which will be listed taking into consideration their timeline and the Phase of the fire they are targeting (A: Prevention & Preparedness, B: Detection & Response, C: Restoration and Adaptation)
- 2) a portfolio of best practice examples and lessons learnt for the different WFRM applications, with an outlook for operationalisation and commercialisation, through links to sections of other platforms, e.g. [EARSC Portal](#) and [Lessons on fire](#)
- 3) training material to boost uptake of WFRM services to meet operational needs in the EU, e.g.: EO science for society and [EO4GEO](#)
- 4) Existing/new publications, articles, papers, fire reports, user manuals of fire technologies and the creation of joint publications by the IAs and by the collaboration occur with the IAs and some stakeholders if possible

Targeted stakeholders: Emergency management organisations; Scientific community; Policy-making bodies; Land management groups; Environmental associations; Media; Society; Industry, technology, and innovation, to find new publications, results and technologies that will help them empower local communities with incentives, exchange good practice, adapt safety rules, develop new tools etc.

3.2.2 *Networking*

3.2.2.1 *Sci-Face Matching Tool*

Firelogue, in its effort to unite not only services and knowledge, but also the researchers and to facilitate their communication, proposes to create a platform called Scientist Face (Sci-face). On this module of the platform, each scientist involved in the IAs will be able to create a profile with his/her name, affiliation, fields of study, information about her/his status (e.g., studies, articles, publications) and contact details. The registration on the Sci-face is voluntary. Within this platform, researchers will match with other researchers with an aim to lead to synergies for joint publications, exchange of views, knowledge and more.

The final decisions for investing in Sci-face will be made through analysing the WFRM community's needs and assessing its usefulness. A very challenging issue of Sci-face is the handling of personal data and Firelogue needs to ensure the safety of the personal information, the content posted and the authenticity of the user and the user's information. The platform's Privacy Policy must be compliant with all relevant regulations as well as GDPR.

Targeted stakeholders: Emergency management organisations; Scientific community; Policy-making bodies; Land management groups; Environmental associations; Industry, technology, and innovation, involved in IAs to create a community of easy knowledge exchange.

3.2.2.2 *News and Events*

A specific feature will be integrated not only in the platform but also in the Firelogue website that will provide project-related information, focusing on the latest dissemination activities; the highlights of Firelogue, IAs and other WFRM related projects (e.g. upcoming events, news, activities); information on announcements of workshops and special sessions in scientific conferences; and announcements of activities open to the public (e.g. press conferences). More specifically, the News & Events page includes the following sub-menus:

1. **News:** presents ongoing wildfire events, articles or paper published in general as well as the project news, such as participations of Firelogue and IAs to meetings; events; conferences; and demonstration pilots. It includes all the records and publications referring to Firelogue which have been published to newspapers and other public channels such as websites, etc.; press releases, containing all the press releases which have been published by Firelogue partners or any other source. Newsletters, which aims to include all the annual Newsletters that will be produced by Firelogue and will be available to inform the interested audience about the latest News of Firelogue.
2. **Events:** presents onto a calendar all the events organized by Firelogue and partners and also all the wildfire-related events, conferences, congresses, workshops, seminars, demonstration pilots, participatory events, aiming to promote the Project and communicate with the various audience such as the wider scientific and academic community; fire practitioners; government and decision makers; the industry and the public addressing to the broader community. More information will be available through clickable links on how to participate redirecting to the conference websites.

Targeted stakeholders: Emergency management organisations; Scientific community; Policy-making bodies; Land management groups; Environmental associations; Media; Society; Industry, technology, and innovation, to have a direct way to be informed for awareness campaigns, new publications, new, events and conferences

and all the “hot” news on new fire-related technologies.

3.2.3 Knowledge Management & Communication

3.2.3.1 Dissemination Booster

Firelogue will streamline the IAs’ activities in seeking support from the EC Dissemination boosters for their exploitation strategies and go-2-market support by launching joint applications. Indicatively, the platforms to be directed from the Firelogue Communication booster to boost IA and [FirEURisk](#) outcomes are shown below:

- 1) [Horizon Results booster](#)
- 2) [Horizon Results Platform](#)
- 3) [European Open Science Cloud](#)
- 4) [The European Technology Transfer Offices Circle](#)
- 5) [European IP Helpdesk](#)
- 6) [The EU Innovation Radar Platform](#)

The above-mentioned platforms are used as repositories of key results of EU-funded Research and Innovation projects. These are the main and prioritised results, selected by each project, with a high potential value to be “exploited”. This means being usable and deriving benefits downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or acting as an important input to policy, further research, or education. A result can be any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge, and information whatever their form or nature.

Through the Firelogue Dissemination Booster, users could be able to find more information about each platform and be prepared to submit a successful application to the above-mentioned platforms. Dissemination Booster is a key feature for Firelogue since one of the project’s goals is to create an impact to European wildfires and beyond and aims to become a portal to the wider market opportunities.

Targeted stakeholders: Emergency management organisations; Scientific community; Policy making bodies; Land management groups; Environmental associations; Industry, technology, and innovation, to benefit from this platform for its services and opportunities for further connections with the EU and EU Market.

3.2.3.2 Technology Market Place (TechMall)

The TechMall refers to a specific feature of the platform that will expose the services provided by each IA and potentially more key WFRM projects. Inside this technology mall there will be descriptions which will refer to tangible services and products that can be used by actors in the entire WFRM value chain. The interested stakeholder will be able to discover what is provided by the IAs, the work they have developed over the years and the contact details of the relevant developer, who would agree to share in the TechMall. The TechMall’s mission is to assist in discovering which services are available and perhaps can be “purchased”; compare services offered by different providers and access to the technology provider. The TechMall will be developed through the following stages:

- 1) **Inventorizing** of operational services and technologies existing or those that are in the development phase, through desk research and input by the involved projects as experts in the WFRM community.
- 2) Identified services will be **grouped** to different WFRM phases (A: Prevention & Preparedness, B: Detection & Response, C: Restoration and Adaptation). During inventorizing, perhaps more grouping ideas may arise to be used.
- 3) **Maturity** assessment. Firstly, the indicators will be identified to capture the maturity levels of a given technology; then information will be gathered against a range of parameters and finally a maturity level will be assigned (initial – basic – intermediate – advanced – optimised).
- 4) Finally, all the information above will be **gathered** to the one “selling point” in the Firelogue platform and be presented along with the relevant contact details of the produces/researcher/developer.

Targeted stakeholders: Emergency management organisations; Scientific community; Policy making bodies; Land management groups; Environmental associations; Industry, technology, and innovation, to look for existing technologies and service providers.

3.2.3.3 Case studies

Firelogue will include a map with all the IA case studies. The information provided by the projects, during the survey of WP1, relevant to their case studies will be presented in the form of tabular portraits. Hence, one portrait will be created for each case study of each project and will include information which is listed in Deliverable 1.1.

Targeted stakeholders: Emergency management organisations; Scientific community; Policy making bodies; Land management groups; Environmental associations; Industry, technology, and innovation.

3.2.3.4 WFRM measures

A specific feature will be also integrated in the platform which will include all the WFRM measures of the IAs will develop apart from technologies. That means everything around policy making, solutions, and/or standard operating procedures. These measures will be depicted in an easy to understand way.

Targeted stakeholders: Emergency management organisations; Scientific community; Policy making bodies; Land management groups; Environmental associations; Industry, technology, and innovation.

3.2.4 Other Functionalities

3.2.4.1 Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ)

The FAQ section has become an important component of websites, either as a stand-alone page or as a website section with multiple subpages per question or topic. Our FAQ page will be an important consideration in the platform design and the Firelogue website, as this section can help the IAs, external stakeholders and citizens to further understand the project and get instant replies to question, related to the WFRM sector, the platform and in general the Firelogue and IAs outcomes. Short answers will be given to

common issues to clarify possible uncertainties and they also represent another way to reach out and connect with our target audiences.

Targeted stakeholders: Emergency management organisations; Scientific community; Policy making bodies; Land management groups; Environmental associations; Media; Society; Industry, technology, and innovation, to get easy access to basic questions and answers.

3.2.4.2 Help Desk

Help Desk is the primary point of contact for all internal and/or external users and is a key tool to provide more support for visitors and propel higher user satisfaction. Firelogue, in the attempt to escape from the trivial use of the simple “Help Desk”, wants to create an environment where the users will be able to ask questions more targeted and address them directly to the specific contact point who will provide the most immediate and direct answer to their issue and become an easy-to-use channel of communication between the various stakeholders of the project. More details about the technical specifications of the platform will be created/available soon after understanding the needs of the IAs.

Targeted stakeholders: Emergency management organisations; Scientific community; Policy making bodies; Land management groups; Environmental associations; Media; Society; Industry, technology, and innovation, to get fast and targeted answers to questions.

4 Conclusion

Firelogue aims at creating a sustainable network in order to enable the engagement of regional stakeholders across the complete WFRM value chain (scientists, policy makers etc.), and to act as an interface to WFRM initiatives. Stakeholder engagement is not only one of the main objectives of Firelogue but also key enabler for the success of its and the IAs activities. To do this, the Firelogue consortium has adopted and implemented an inclusive stakeholder engagement strategy described in this Deliverable, which must be clear to all partners of the consortium.

To engage effectively the Firelogue users, Firelogue develops the Communication Booster which is designed using state-of-the-art technology to fully accommodate the requirements stemming from its purpose. The booster is a centralised information platform for both IAs results and existing WFRM information. It will include information in a user-friendly environment and many more features that will be assessed for their usefulness with IA and external stakeholders during the next period.

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